

CONTINGENCY MEASURES OF EXISTING HOTEL ESTABLISHMENTS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract:

This study aimed to examine and determine the contingency measures used by selected hotel establishments in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental, in light of the COVID-19 pandemic, and evaluate the hypothesis. The present study was based on the hospitality industry's crisis management and contingency planning discipline. A descriptive-correlational research design was applied, and a researcher-made instrument was utilized, which underwent a dry run and yielded a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.862, confirming its reliability. Most respondents were female, aged 30–49, college graduates, regular-permanent employees with less than three years of service, and serving in supervisory roles. The results showed a high level and significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in implementing contingency measures regarding safety protocol requirements and inventory management when grouped according to length of service and job position. As a result, the hotel establishments in Bacolod City have been successfully upgraded, especially leveraging revenue management and safety protocols, with moderate implementation in human resources and inventory management. The researcher recommends that the hotel establishments strengthen their human resources and inventory contingency practices and institutionalize pandemic preparedness protocols. Future studies may also explore leadership style, technological adaptation, and guest satisfaction during crises.

Keywords: Covid-19 pandemic, contingency measures, hotel establishments, management of revenue, human resource, inventory management, safety protocol requirements, correlation, Bacolod City, Negros Occidental

Introduction:

The hospitality industry is one of the most feasible and productive industries, with considerable expansion and development opportunities. The hospitality sector offers both economic opportunities and recreational services, making it an important contributor to regional development. The researcher was interested in how hotel managers deal with the daily devastation caused by a pandemic and how well-defined and functional the COVID-19 contingency plans are. The world's economic hospitality industry has been devastated by the pandemic caused by the COVID-19 disease outbreak. The current situation has prompted many countries to enact restrictive measures to halt the spread of the virus. The record shows that the much-displaced hospitality and tourism workforce is currently jobless and replaced due to the current situation. During previous pandemics in the tourism industry, solutions were implemented in the current state of uncertainty.

Most studies focus on economic risks and their consequences on tourist flows and monetary income. Economic and financial activities have classified policies to mitigate the negative impact of COVID-19. Nonetheless, few have specifically investigated hotel managers' measures to ensure their guests' health and safety. Organizational structure can range from mild concerns, such as employee medical problems, to massive commercial destruction wrought by crises and catastrophic events. This variation is classified into cycles based on how much harm they cause organizations. Cases involving pandemics and natural disasters are divided into four categories: pre-crisis, crisis, post-crisis, and long-term recovery. Another viewpoint examined crises beginning with an emergency phase with no return point; an intermediate phase where recovery may take several years; and a long-term phase where the economy and market will recover quickly. Because of the time scale involved in each stage, different responses and strategies may require planning and managing the results. The transition between stages can result in either a worsening or a recovery stage.

The Department of Tourism (DOT) is directed to issue guidelines for exercising the mandate of the President of the Republic of the Philippines under the Bayanihan to Heal as One Act under the Memorandum of the Executive Secretary dated March 28, 2020. This states that all hospitality practitioners must follow all the necessary guidelines. Governments made contingency plans based on comprehensive and structured approaches of crisis prevention to rejuvenate the hotel industry, such as preserving vital services to decrease the country's infrastructure and social life risk; stretching antiviral solutions to prevent mortality rates, and strengthening healthcare services to halt and reduce the transmission of the infection.

The pandemic's implications are clearly and considerably significant; hence, the researcher decided to do this research. The study aims to increase hotel managers' and supervisors' collective perception and countermeasures regarding COVID-19 in the hotel sector, economic income, and employment. It can enlighten people to follow the

new protocol to prevent it from spreading. Residents and the government will benefit from reduced health risks. By adhering to travel protocols, the government would not have to impose travel limits, and many establishments and industries could reopen, resulting in a thriving economy.

Local tourism is steadily recovering, hotels are open for business, with retired workers slowly rehired. On the other hand, company owners restrict their granted career opportunities due to the pandemic's growing emphasis. Even though this is positive progress, the country's employment situation remains a primary concern. Tourists can now travel after the travel bans have lifted. However, they must meet government-mandated procedures, such as applying health and safety certificates, so that officials can verify that the destinations are safe to return their guests. Throughout this circumstance, the ideal way to limit virus spread is to adopt the government's new guidelines, useful in formulating necessary interventions and measures to prevent the Covid-19 pandemic's consequences and minimize health risks.

Literature Review:

The COVID-19 pandemic caused an unprecedented disruption in the global tourism and hospitality industry. Hotel establishments faced major operational challenges due to strict health protocols, reduced mobility, and sudden economic decline. These circumstances necessitated implementing contingency measures to ensure business continuity and guest safety. (Filimonau et al., 2020)

The hotel sector significantly contributes to economic development and employment in many regions (Dogru et al., 2024). During the pandemic, however, the industry experienced dramatic revenue losses, mass layoffs, and temporary closures (Blair et al., 2021). COVID-19 altered consumer behavior and compelled hospitality businesses to adopt operational adjustments, such as enhanced sanitation, limited capacity, and remote working arrangements for non-essential staff Y. Vigilia, (2021).

The dramatic drop in global tourism, with hotels experiencing historically low occupancy rates (Garrido-Moreno et al., 2021). This led to adopting various contingency strategies focused on health safety, resource optimization, and crisis communication (Tiwari, 2024). A study by Berihe (2020) noted that Ethiopian hotels implemented rigorous hygiene protocols, reduced workforce hours, and diversified service offerings to cope with the pandemic's effects. Similarly, scholars like Dolnicar & Zare (2020) emphasized how hotels in Poland adjusted their operations based on the geographic spread of COVID-19. Their findings revealed that hotel performance was directly influenced by regional case rates, with urban areas facing higher impacts. The study emphasized the importance of proactive contingency planning and risk mitigation.

The crisis also highlighted the need for stronger government support and flexible business models (Lewis et al., 2023). The pandemic underscored the importance of public-private partnerships in the tourism sector. Regional policies and local recovery plans, such as those recommended by Baggio et al., (2010), became essential in guiding hotel establishments toward long-term sustainability.

In the Philippine context, the tourism and hospitality industry was similarly affected. According to local reports, hotel establishments in cities like Bacolod had to quickly respond by implementing safety protocols, adjusting pricing strategies, and retraining staff for multi-skilling tasks. Many establishments also adopted technology-based solutions such as contactless payments, online bookings, and virtual concierge services (Aquino et al., 2021; Tayco et al., 2023).

Overall, the literature suggests that contingency measures from revenue management to safety compliance are essential for hotels to survive crises. However, these strategies' effectiveness largely depends on leadership adaptability, employee preparedness, and institutional support.

Methodology:

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive correlational research design using the self-made survey questionnaire to determine the contingency measures of existing hotel establishments during Covid-19 pandemic in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental.

Table 1
Sample Distribution of Respondents

Hotel Establishment	Sample Size (n)	Proportion (%)
Hotel A	12	20.00
Hotel B	12	20.00

Hotel C	12	20.00
Hotel D	12	20.00
Hotel E	12	20.00
Total	60	100.00

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents. Using purposive sampling technique there were twelve (12) hotel managers or supervisor representing each of the five (5) selected hotel establishments in Bacolod City, constituting 20% per establishment respectively. So there was a total sixty (60) respondents (100%).

Research Instrument

The researcher-made survey-questionnaire was used to gather data about the level of implementation of the contingency measures of existing hotel establishments during Covid-19 pandemic in terms of revenue management, human resources, inventory management and safety protocol requirements.

The instrument was composed of three (3) parts. The first (1st) part contains items about the respondents' profile in terms of age, gender, highest educational qualification, employment status, length of service, and job position and a researcher made checklist was employed. The second (2nd) part contains items about the level of implementation of the contingency measures of existing hotel establishments during Covid-19 Pandemic in terms of revenue management, human resources, inventory management, and safety protocol requirements. The following scale with interpretation was followed:

Scale	Description	Verbal Description
4	Highly Implemented	This means the respondent assesses that contingency measures is implemented at the existing hotel establishments during Covid-19 pandemic in all instances.
3	Moderately Implemented	This means the respondent assesses that contingency measures is implemented at the existing hotel establishments during Covid-19 pandemic in many instances.
2	Less Implemented	This means the respondent assesses that contingency measures is implemented at the existing hotel establishments during the Covid-19 pandemic in few instances.
1	Highly Implemented	This means the respondent assesses that contingency measures is implemented at the existing hotel establishments during Covid-19 pandemic at all times.

The third (3rd) part pertains to the problems encountered by respondents on the level of implementation of contingency measures of existing hotel establishments in terms of problem management, management style, management support, and multi-skilling. The following scale with interpretation was followed:

Scale	Description	Verbal Description
4	Very Serious	This means the respondent assesses that he or she encountered problems in the implementation of contingency measures at the existing hotel establishments during Covid-19 pandemic in all instances.
3	Serious	This means the respondent assesses that he or she encountered problems in the implementation of contingency measures at the existing hotel establishments during Covid-19 pandemic in few instances.
2	Less Serious	This means the respondent assesses that contingency measures is implemented at the existing hotel establishments during the Covid-19 pandemic in few instances.
1	Not Serious	This means the respondent assesses that he or she did not encounter problem in the implementation of contingency measures at the existing hotel establishments during Covid-19 pandemic in many instances.

Dry Run Procedure

A dry-run procedure was conducted at Sugarland Hotel among the employees to test the reliability of the self-made questionnaire. Ten (10) individuals served as dry-run respondents. They were not part of the final administration of

the survey questionnaire to avoid the incidence of familiarity and bias. Incidences of non-response were also noted in the revision and finalization of the self-made questionnaire.

The Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.862321 indicates that the self-made survey tool was reliable for final administration to the target respondents.

Research Procedure

Gathering of Data. The researcher wrote a letter addressed to the hotel owners or managers in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental, asking permission to conduct research noted by the adviser through endorsement and recommending approval from the Dean of the graduate school. After the letter was approved, the survey questionnaires were distributed to the respondents within two (2) weeks. Upon completing the survey, the researcher manually collected and tabulated the data. The data gathered was examined, analyzed, and interpreted.

Treatment of Data. The following statistical tools were used in the study:

Frequency Count and Percentage were used to summarize, analyze, and interpret the profile of the respondents.

Weighted Mean was used to summarize, analyze, and interpret the responses to implementing contingency measures of existing hotel establishments during the COVID-19 pandemic and the problems encountered.

Chi-square test of independence was used to determine the significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their responses on the level of implementation of contingency measures of existing hotel establishments during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Findings

Based on the data gathered, the following findings of this study were drawn:

1. The majority of the respondents were 30 to 49 years old, female, college graduates, had regular-permanent employment status, had 3 years or less of length of service, and worked as supervisors in the hotel establishments in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental.
2. The managers and supervisors at the existing hotel establishments in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental, *highly implemented* contingency measures in terms of revenue management and safety protocol requirements, while human resources and inventory management were *moderately implemented*.
3. The respondents disclosed that they encountered *very serious* problems in implementing the contingency measures at the hotel establishments in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental, in the aspects of problem management and multi-skilling, and *serious* problems in the area of management style and management support.
4. There is a significant relationship between the respondents' length of service and their responses on the level of implementation of contingency measures in terms of safety protocol requirements. There is also a significant relationship between the respondents' job position and their responses on implementing contingency measures in inventory management.

Discussion

Profile of the Respondents. This section presents the respondents' profiles in terms of age, gender, educational qualification, employment status, length of service, and job position, which determines the level of implementation of the contingency measures of the existing hotel establishments. There was an equal number of respondents per hotel establishment who took part in this study.

Table 2 presents the data of the frequencies and percentage distribution of the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, educational qualification, employment status, length of service and job position.

Table 2
Profile of the Respondents

Profile Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Age		
• 50 years old and above	4	6.67
• 30 - 49 years old	32	53.33
• 18 - 29 years old	24	40.00
Gender		
• Female	35	58.33
• Male	25	41.67
Educational Qualification		

• Post Graduate	3	5.00
• College Graduate	53	88.33
• College Level	4	6.67
Employment Status		
• Regular- Permanent	55	91.67
• Probationary	4	6.6
• Seasonal - Contractual	1	1.67
Length of Service		
• 15 years and above	4	6.67
• 10 to 14 years	10	16.67
• 4 to 9 years	10	16.67
• 3 years & below	18	30.00
Job Position		
• Manager	12	20.00
• Supervisor	48	80.00

The results show that most hotel personnel in managerial and supervisory roles in Bacolod City are aged 30 to 49 (53.33%), suggesting a mature and experienced workforce. Meanwhile, 40% are between 18 and 29, indicating the growing presence of younger leaders in the industry. The survey's small number of respondents aged 50 years and older (6.67%) may indicate early retirement or new transitions into consultancy positions. Hanushek et al., (2025) also argue that professionals in the 30–49 age range are often at their peak in terms of skills and competencies, being the most productive in terms of efficiency.

In terms of gender, 58.33% of respondents were female, reflecting the increasing presence of women in hotel leadership (Dashper (2020)). This gender representation highlights the industry's evolving inclusivity and leadership diversity.

A small percentage of respondents had not completed a degree at 6.67%. This indicates the standard for a supervisory or managerial role is a college degree, as supported by the findings of Olowoyo et al., (2020) on the worth of academic preparation in hospitality operations.

Regarding employment status, 91.67 % were regular or permanent employees, suggesting the jobs are stable and there is commitment to the workforce as an investment that supports long-term employment, which could be important to the recovery from the pandemic (Khan et al., 2021).

On length of service, 30% had been in their position for three years or less, 33.34% had served for between 4 and 14 years, and only 6.67% had served for over 15 years. Tews et al., (2020) reported that younger professionals perceive better opportunities, whilst those who had spent a long time at an organization have the added experience of institutional knowledge.

Finally, 80% of respondents were supervisors and 20% were managers, indicating that middle management plays a crucial role in hotel operations. As stated by Chen et al., (2023) supervisors are essential in enforcing standards, managing teams, and maintaining service quality.

Overall, the demographic profile reflects a stable, educated, and female-dominated supervisory workforce, underscoring the hotel industry's emphasis on leadership continuity, professional development, and gender inclusivity in Bacolod City.

Table 3
Level of Implementation in Terms of Revenue Management

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Gross operating profit per available room.	3.53	Highly Implemented
2. Total revenue per available room.	3.60	Highly Implemented
3. Net revenue per available room.	3.53	Highly Implemented
4. Average revenue per account.	3.42	Highly Implemented
5. Earnings before interest, taxes, depreciation and amortization.	3.43	Highly Implemented
6. Average daily rate.	3.38	Highly Implemented
7. Occupancy rate.	3.62	Highly Implemented
Aggregate Mean	3.50	Highly Implemented

The highest weighted mean of 3.62 shows respondents agreed that contingency measures on revenue management were highly implemented, specifically in monitoring occupancy. This indicates that hotel management would have ensured that occupancy levels were high enough to operate, even allowing for lower guest numbers due

to travel restrictions imposed during COVID-19. This suggests that hotel management ensured occupancy levels were sufficient to sustain operations despite the decline in guests due to travel restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic.

While still high, the lowest mean of 3.38 indicates that computing the daily average rate was also consistently practiced. This allowed hotels to estimate their break-even income even with reduced guest arrivals. The overall mean of 3.50 confirms that contingency measures on revenue management were highly implemented across the selected hotels in Bacolod City.

These findings support that the pandemic severely affected the hospitality industry, leading to decreased occupancy, revenue loss, and operational challenges. Studies by Biwota (2020) and Hao et al.,(2020) emphasize how lockdowns and cancellations caused major financial setbacks for hotels, prompting them to adapt their financial strategies for survival.

Table 4
Level of Implementation in Terms of Human Resources

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Laid off, furloughed or unpaid leave accounts	3.23	Moderately Implemented
2. Expand access to paid leave	3.00	Moderately Implemented
3. Adopt work arrangement	3.33	Highly Implemented
4. Implement employment retention measures	3.18	Moderately Implemented
5. Provide financial assistance and other means	3.13	Moderately Implemented
6. Apply collective bargaining and labor relations	3.07	Moderately Implemented
Aggregate Mean	3.16	Moderately Implemented

The highest weighted mean of 3.33 shows contingency measures in human resources, and the data show that adopting alternative work arrangements was highly implemented. Due to government restrictions and reduced guest numbers, hotels adjusted employee schedules by assigning work-from-home setups and skeletal shifts.

The lowest mean of 3.16 indicates that expanding access to paid leave was only moderately implemented. Many employees were placed under a no-work-no-pay scheme, but some received financial support through unused leave credits, as allowed by DOLE.

The overall mean of 3.16 suggests moderate implementation of HR measures. Hotels in Bacolod City tried to balance employee welfare with financial limitations during the pandemic. Lockdowns and limited travel affected hotel revenues, forcing management to cut costs and reduce staff. The Human Resource departments must adapt to such challenges to maintain organizational effectiveness and long-term resilience (Rajamanthri, 2021).

Table 5
Level of Implementation in Terms of Inventory Management

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Inventory turn-over	3.05	Moderately Implemented
2. Stock outs	3.15	Moderately Implemented
3. Inactive stocks	3.17	Moderately Implemented
4. Loss sales	3.40	Highly Implemented
5. Carrying cost of inventory	3.38	Highly Implemented
6. Order Cycle Time	3.25	Highly Implemented
Aggregate Mean	3.23	Moderately Implemented

The highest weighted mean of 3.40 indicates that contingency measures in inventory management data show that adjusting supply procurement was highly implemented. Hotels reduced purchases for rooms, restrooms, and restaurants to manage losses during closures and low-income periods.

The lowest mean of 3.05 shows that inventory turnover measures were moderately implemented. Due to limited revenue, hotels calculated how quickly inventory was used and replaced to better control stock levels and costs. With an overall mean of 3.23, the findings suggest that inventory management measures were moderately

implemented. Hotel managers monitored supplies' ordering, storage, and usage to ensure proper stock levels during uncertain operations.

The pandemic significantly disrupted hotel sales and inventory. Hotels, which typically purchase in bulk for smooth service, faced losses from unsold stock due to low occupancy. Health protocols, visitor limits, and sanitation requirements further slowed recovery (Escribano-Navas & Gemar, 2021).

IATF-EID travel bans and restrictions starting in March 2020 caused widespread booking cancellations and disrupted hotel operations. Delays in supply deliveries due to transport limitations also impacted inventory cycles. The global travel restrictions hindered the movement of essential supplies, compounding operational challenges in the hospitality industry (Devi, 2020).

Table 6
Level of Implementation of in Terms of Safety Protocol

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Face covering required.	3.57	Highly Implemented
2. Practice Social distancing	3.58	Highly Implemented
3. Temperature Monitoring Kiosks	3.58	Highly Implemented
4. Screening and Testing	3.55	Highly Implemented
5. Contact Tracing	3.50	Highly Implemented
6. Health Declaration Form upon check in.	3.58	Highly Implemented
7. Online Payment upon booking	3.18	Moderately Implemented
8. Proper disposal of used PPE	3.13	Moderately Implemented
9. Practice of proper hand washing etiquette/hand hygiene, respiratory etiquette, and proper use of face mask	3.58	Highly Implemented
Aggregate Mean	3.45	Highly Implemented

The highest weighted mean of 3.58 indicates that safety protocols such as social distancing, temperature checks, health declarations, hand hygiene, and mask-wearing were highly implemented. Shows the strong efforts of hotel managers and supervisors to ensure the health and safety of employees and guests during the pandemic.

The lowest mean of 3.13 suggests that proper disposal of used PPE was only moderately implemented. While hotels took measures to dispose of protective equipment safely, consistent compliance remained a challenge.

The overall mean of 3.45 shows that safety protocol measures were moderately implemented across the selected hotels in Bacolod City. Although hotels complied with government mandates from the DOH, DOT, and IATF-EID, they faced challenges such as non-cooperative guests, swab test results, and false health declarations, which sometimes disrupted operations and contact tracing efforts.

These findings imply that while hotels strived to meet health standards, enforcement and compliance were not always seamless. The hotel industry continues to face challenges in maintaining effective safety measures amidst evolving public health concerns (Rueda López et al., 2021).

Table 7
Summarized Data on the Level of Implementation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
Revenue Management	3.50	Highly Implemented
Human Resources	3.16	Moderately Implemented
Inventory Management	3.23	Moderately Implemented
Safety Protocol Requirements	3.45	Highly Implemented
Overall Mean	3.33	Highly Implemented

The highest aggregate mean of 3.45 indicates that safety protocols were highly implemented, showing that hotel managers and supervisors in Bacolod City took active steps to prevent the spread of COVID-19. Measures included strict adherence to health guidelines to protect both staff and guests.

In contrast, the lowest aggregate mean of 3.16 suggests that human resource measures were only moderately implemented. While hotels adjusted employee schedules and offered limited financial assistance, these efforts were constrained by available resources.

The overall mean of 3.33 implies that hotels in Bacolod City generally implemented effective contingency measures to sustain operations during the pandemic. Despite these efforts, travel restrictions, lockdowns, and low guest turnout significantly declined revenue and occupancy.

The hotel establishments adopted cost-saving strategies and liquidity management plans, but the impact of the crisis remained overwhelming. Health-related anxiety among staff persisted due to fear of infection, misinformation, and vaccine hesitancy, further complicating recovery efforts (El-Said et al., 2023; Selem et al., 2022).

Table 8

Problems Encountered by the Respondents in Implementing the Contingency Measures at the Hotel Establishments in Terms of Problem Management

Indictors	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Diagnose problems immediately and pinpoint the root cause in a given time	3.42	Very Serious
2. Fix problems immediately	3.27	Very Serious
3. Record and solve problems in a given time	3.25	Very Serious
4. Resolve number of incidents in a given time	3.18	Serious
Aggregate Mean	3.36	Very Serious

The highest weighted mean of 3.42 indicates that respondents faced serious problems in problem management, particularly in quickly diagnosing issues and identifying root causes. The operational changes required by DOH, DOT, and IATF-EID protocols posed unprecedented challenges for hotels.

The lowest mean of 3.18 shows serious difficulties in resolving incidents promptly, largely due to reduced staff availability caused by decreased revenue from travel bans and lockdowns.

With an aggregate mean of 3.36, hotel managers in Bacolod City experienced significant problem identification and resolution challenges, compounded by limited financial resources during the pandemic.

During the early pandemic phase, hotels suffered from sharp declines in occupancy due to lockdowns. To cope, many reduced expenses by laying off employees, cutting supplies, and raising room rates though higher rates risked further discouraging guests facing financial hardship.

According to Yacoub & ElHajjar (2021) crises as transitions requiring urgent responses rather than mere dilemmas, highlighting the need for adaptive crisis management.

Table 9

Level of Seriousness of Problems Encountered by the Respondents in Implementing the Contingency Measures at the Hotel Establishments in Terms of Management Style

Indictors	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Pragmatists (driven, competitive and they value hitting their goals above all else)	3.28	Very Serious
2. Idealists (want to learn and grow, and they want everyone else on the team to do the same)	3.22	Serious
3. Stewards (are dependable, loyal and helpful, and they provide a stabilizing and calming force their team members)	3.05	Serious
4. Diplomats (are the affiliate force that keeps groups together and typically build deep personal bonds with their employees)	3.13	Serious
Aggregate Mean	3.20	Serious

The highest weighted mean of 3.28 indicates that respondents faced serious problems related to leadership style, especially pragmatism; managers struggled to address issues realistically and practically amid the crisis.

The lowest mean of 3.05 reflects serious challenges with stewardship leadership, where managers found it difficult to provide stability, loyalty, and support during the new normal.

An overall mean of 3.36 shows that hotel leaders in Bacolod City encountered significant obstacles in demonstrating effective leadership qualities such as pragmatism, idealism, stewardship, and diplomacy.

Hotel management had to develop and adjust action plans in line with government health protocols enforcing social distancing, contact tracing, regular disinfection, and minimizing guest capacity. Implementing these measures was challenging, especially with financial losses and the need to innovate operational practices.

The unpredictable pandemic severely impacted worldwide crisis management and leadership effectiveness in the hospitality sector (Alzoubi & Jaaffar, 2020).

Table 10

Level of Seriousness of the Problems Encountered by the Respondents in Implementing the Contingency Measures at the Hotel Establishments in Terms of Management Support.

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Budgetary provision	3.38	Very Serious
2. Utilization of training provision	3.05	Serious
3. Attitude of the management towards training	3.25	Very Serious
4. Creating a sense of change urgency	3.27	Very Serious
5. Creating or developing a company change guiding coalition or alliance	3.08	Serious
6. Developing a vision of the required company future state and a strategy to achieve it	3.18	Serious
7. Communicating the vision and strategy to the entire workforce	3.15	Serious
8. Creating an environment in the company where associate empowerment can evolve	3.25	Very Serious
Aggregate Mean	3.18	Serious

The highest weighted mean of 3.38 shows respondents faced serious problems with management support, especially budgetary provision. Due to decreased hotel income amid the pandemic, management hesitated to spend, limiting necessary expenses.

The lowest mean of 3.05 indicates serious issues with utilizing training provisions. Government-mandated closures and financial losses led to workforce reductions, making employee training a lower priority.

An overall mean of 3.18 reflects significant challenges in securing management support. Due to management's cautious spending, employees struggled to obtain budgets for essential supplies like sanitizers, PPE, and renovations.

To cope, some hotels temporarily closed or considered bankruptcy, while others with emergency funds operated under strict protocols, including online bookings to reduce contact. Delays often occurred due to required contact tracing when infected guests were identified.

These findings imply that reduced revenues severely impacted budget allocations, hindering operational support. Maja (2016) emphasizes that businesses must innovate management practices continuously to survive in such dynamic environments.

Table 11

Level of Seriousness of the Problems Encountered by the Respondents in Implementing the Contingency Measures at the Hotel Establishments in Terms of Multi-Skilling

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Boosts confidence of the staff	3.30	Very serious
2. Edge above the specialized staff	3.23	Serious
3. Better productivity leads to better quality	3.30	Very Serious
4. Efficiency in the business	3.37	Very Serious
5. Less turnover ratio (bonus, promotion, remuneration)	3.15	Serious
Aggregate Mean	3.25	Very Serious

The highest weighted mean of 3.37 indicates that respondents encountered serious problems related to multi-skilling, particularly in maintaining business efficiency. Hotel operations in Bacolod City faced severe challenges due to months-long closures and limited activity during the quarantine.

The lowest mean of 3.15 reveals serious issues in reducing employee turnover through incentives like bonuses and promotions. With limited funds, hotel management struggled to retain skilled staff and provide adequate financial support.

Table 13

Results on the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Profile and their Responses on the Level of Implementation of Contingency Measures of Existing Hotel Establishments During the Covid-19 Pandemic

Indicators	df	Computed Value	Critical Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Age in relation to:					
• Revenue Management	4	0.812	9.488	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Human Resource	6	2.905	12.592	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Inventory Management	4	4.851	9.488	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Safety Protocol Requirements	6	13.042	12.592	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Gender in relation to:					
• Revenue Management	2	0.476	5.991	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Human Resource	3	2.227	7.815	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Inventory Management	2	1.802	5.991	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Safety Protocol Requirements	3	3.556	7.815	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Educational Qualification in relation to:					
• Revenue Management	4	9.417	9.488	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Human Resource	6	3.557	12.592	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Inventory Management	4	4.704	9.488	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Safety Protocol Requirements	6	5.907	12.592	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Employment Status in relation to:					
• Revenue Management	4	4.202	9.488	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Human Resource	5	4.27	11.070	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Inventory Management	4	2.207	9.488	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Safety Protocol Requirements	6	2.338	12.592	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Length of Service in relation to:					
• Revenue Management	6	1.221	12.592	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Human Resource	9	13.616	16.919	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Inventory Management	6	9.572	12.592	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Safety Protocol Requirements	9	19.762	16.919	Failed to Reject Ho	Significant (C=0.50; moderate)
Job Position in relation to:					
• Revenue Management	2	1.342	5.991	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

• Human Resource	3	4.499	7.815	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Inventory Management	2	10.844	5.991	Reject Ho	Significant (C=0.39; slight)
• Safety Protocol Requirements	3	4.167	7.815	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

An overall mean of 3.25 suggests hotels faced significant challenges implementing multi-skilling measures. Staff, as front liners, experienced stress and anxiety about virus exposure, often choosing to distance themselves from family. The lack of training on virus transmission and safety protocols heightened their fears. Infections among staff also led to workforce reductions due to contact tracing and quarantine, further affecting operations.

These problems highlight how efficiency was seriously disrupted. Support this by noting that COVID-19 placed immense strain on the fragile tourism and hospitality sectors, underscoring the urgent need for employee multi-skilling, improved hygiene awareness, crisis preparedness, and stronger support systems (Rana, 2021).

Conclusion:

The onslaught of the COVID-19 pandemic adversely affected the sustainability of the tourism and hospitality industry worldwide due to implementing community quarantine for many months to curb the fast transmission of the deadly virus. During the imposition of the community quarantine, the non-essential business entities were under closure order by the government authorities for an indefinite period. So during this period, the management of the hotels needed to implement contingency measures to enable the business to hold on and be sustainable despite the loss of income for many months and slow recovery due to the limited number of guests that would check in and other events that were usually the source of income for the hotels. Further, with the slow operations, the management had to contend with limited revenue to cover the expenses and follow the government's health and safety protocols.

Moreover, since the problems in the hotel operations were not experienced before, considering that the Covid-19 pandemic was unprecedented. The managers and supervisors experienced challenges finding solutions and keeping the skilled workers due to limited financial resources to pay their salaries and benefits.

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